

REQUIREMENTS FOR AN OPEN SEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF A VERTICAL PROVIDER

L. Martin*, F. Engl, A. Henrich, University of Bamberg, 96047 Bamberg, Germany

Abstract

A major advantage of an Open Search Infrastructure, as propagated by the Open Search Foundation¹, should be that it facilitates the development of special search solutions for special purposes, so-called verticals. In order to design a beneficial infrastructure in this respect, it is crucial to understand the requirements from the perspective of a vertical provider. Therefore, in this extended abstract we describe the requirements that result from our experiences with the IT-Atlas Upper Franconia.

MOTIVATION

Starting in 2014 we created a small vertical search engine for local IT companies² in cooperation with an IT business association in Upper Franconia [1]. There are some specific ideas implemented in this search engine: We do not search for documents (web pages) but for companies described by web pages. To derive the company ranking for a query, we fit web pages vote for their company [2]. Furthermore, topic modelling [3] is used to improve the search results by injecting domain knowledge. The search engine result page (SERP) lists small automatically generated and query dependent profiles of the best ranked companies. In the remainder of this extended abstract we will sketch the requirements which arise if such a “company search” should be implemented on the basis of an Open Search Infrastructure.

A COMMON INDEX TO SEARCH

To avoid the need for a custom index, the search for company web pages relevant to a query has to be executed on an index provided by the infrastructure. Of course, this initially requires limiting the search to pages of specific web domains. However, there are further wishes: since the pages found vote for the relevant companies [2], it seems reasonable to have not only pages of a domain itself, but also pages that are directly linked from this domain in the results. Furthermore, we mentioned above that we use domain-related resources (e.g. thesauri, topic models, or ontologies) to optimise the ranking. It should therefore be possible for the vertical to inject corresponding resources to the central index such that it takes them into account in the ranking, similar to the relationship of WordPress and Typo3 being WCMS.

DOCUMENT DATA STORE

For generating snippets in the SERPs—which are usually query dependent—search engines commonly use a docu-

ment data store [4, p. 16]. To allow for rich company descriptions in the SERP of a vertical it is necessary that the document data store contains not only information on web page level, but also on web site level and, where applicable, even on brand or company level. This could be achieved by interlinking among the different levels and connecting to knowledge graphs like Wikidata³. A rather specific aspect is that our current search engine integrates thumbnails of the companies’ landing pages into the SERP. It can hardly be required from an infrastructure to provide such specific assets but this example shows that verticals will have the need to build their own add-ons to the document data store. Here, clear interfaces and update mechanisms are needed.

CRAWL DATA FOR LANGUAGE MODELS

As mentioned above, the current version of the company search uses a topic model [3] to enhance the ranking and the result presentation. One could of course use other techniques as well but the shared requirement is to perform some type of corpus analysis on a well defined subset of the crawled web corpus. Regarding our search engine, this subset consists of IT-related documents (e.g. web pages) in German (we will not discuss the aspects of many web pages containing information in their local language and in English here). One solution for this feature request would be to allow the download of a defined subset of the corpus. A more resource efficient solution for the client (vertical provider) would be an API for executing the analyzer on the server side, similar to concepts like FaaS (e.g. AWS Lambda⁴) or Apache Spark⁵.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Blank, S. Boosz, and A. Henrich, “IT company atlas upper franconia: A practical application of expert search techniques,” in *Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, Pisa, Italy, April 4-8, 2016*, ACM, 2016, pp. 1048–1053. doi: 10.1145/2851613.2851695.
- [2] A. Henrich and M. Wegmann, “Search and evaluation methods for class level information retrieval: Extended use and evaluation of methods applied in expertise retrieval,” in *SAC ’21: The 36th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing, Virtual Event, Republic of Korea, March 22-26, 2021*, ACM, 2021, pp. 681–684. doi: 10.1145/3412841.3442092.
- [3] D. M. Blei, “Probabilistic topic models,” *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 27, pp. 55–65, 2012.
- [4] W. B. Croft, D. Metzler, and T. Strohman, *Search engines: Information retrieval in practice*. Addison-Wesley Reading, 2010, vol. 520.

* leon.martin@uni-bamberg.de

¹ <https://opensearchfoundation.org> (accessed 15/06/2021)

² <https://it-atlas-oberfranken.de> (accessed 15/06/2021)

³ <https://wikidata.org> (accessed 15/06/2021)

⁴ <https://aws.amazon.com/de/lambda> (accessed 15/06/2021)

⁵ <https://spark.apache.org> (accessed 15/06/2021)